

FIELD-TUNABLE COMPOSITES WITH GLASS-COATED Co-BASED MAGNETIC MICROWIRES

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SUMMARY

Composite media containing glass-coated Co-rich amorphous microwires are designed and fashioned. It is shown that the wire magnetic properties strongly affect the dielectric response of the composite. A model is presented to account for these observations. The microwave dielectric function is found to depend on the microwave impedance of the wire.

Keywords: Glass-coated amorphous microwires; Magnetic property; Microwires-dielectric composite; Microwave transmission; Field-tunable composite.

INTRODUCTION

The design and development of novel composite materials with optimized properties is of relevance to study new phenomena and to use them in new generation advanced sensing elements. In this regard, composite media with periodic arrays of scattering elements has received much attention because they allow a selective spectral response for electromagnetic irradiation. In electrodynamics of composite, conductive wire inclusion may induce unusual polarisation properties in response to the microwave. Magnetic microwires are attracting increasing interest as they are ideal materials for the study of fundamental micromagnetic problems and are suitable for a number of technological applications, particularly in sensor technologies [1]. Two types of soft magnetic microwires are currently studied: water-quenched amorphous wires [2] with a diameter of around 120 μm , and quenched and drawn microwires with diameters ranging from 2 to 20 μm [3], covered by a protective insulating glassy coat. Recently, a new family of composite materials with glass coated magnetic amorphous microwires has been introduced such as remote non-destructive self-testing media [4]. The design of such composite materials with glass coated magnetic amorphous microwires is of special scientific interest due to a large sensitivity of the effective permittivity to a dc magnetic field [5]-[6]. The theoretical aspects of wire containing composite are also developed [7]. It has been shown that the magnetic behaviour of the microwires especially its giant magneto impedance (GMI) strongly depends on their dimensions and compositions [1].

One typical composition of microwire is (Fe,Co,Ni,Mn)-(Mo,Si,B) exhibiting a coercive field (H_c) of 0.1-10 Oe [8]. Amorphous microwires are soft magnetic materials and their magnetization change can be made by a small magnetic field. Such microwires, like Co-based microwires, possess the giant magnetoimpedance (GMI) effect are being intensively studied for sensor applications [1]. In Co-rich microwires with negative magnetostriction and a circular domain structure, magnetization rotates in the direction of the axis by a field of a few Oe, which is accompanied by large changes in impedance in the range of 100% in GHz frequencies [9]. In particular, magnetic properties depend mostly on the magnetoelastic anisotropy arising from the coupling of the internal stress with magnetostriction constant [10].

While the potential use of these materials in sensing technologies has been demonstrated previously, the present work aims to present recent results concerning field tunable scattering spectra at microwave frequencies in glass-fibre reinforced composite media containing CoFeNiSiBMo amorphous microwires and open the way to new applications.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Sample preparation

Glass covered microwires (Co,Fe,Ni)-(B,Si,Mo) with different geometric ratio of metallic nucleus diameter to total microwire diameter (see Table 1) were fabricated by the Taylor-Ulitovsky method [11]. The precursor microwire consists of an amorphous nucleus, with nominal composition and diameter pointed in Table 1, and vanishing magnetostriction of -3×10^{-7} . The amorphous structure of the wire was confirmed by X-ray Diffraction (XRD). Scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used for examining the samples prepared by cross-section polishing.

Four layers of E-glass epoxy prepreg 913 (with in-plane size 50x50 cm) were used as the matrix for composite samples whose thickness is about 0.64 mm. The long microwires (length – 50 cm) were aligned parallel as periodic lattice with different spacing between wires. The composite with different wire composition and different period of wire distribution are obtained (see Table 2).

Table 1. Characteristics of microwires including compositions, the core diameter (D), and the total diameter (D_w), saturation magnetisation (M_s), coercive force (H_c), anisotropy field (H_a).

Composition	D , μM	D_w , μm	M_s , Gs	H_c , Oe	H_a , Oe
$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	18.6	24.2	10789	0.30	3.4
$\text{Fe}_{3.85}\text{Co}_{67.05}\text{Ni}_{1.44}\text{B}_{11.53}\text{Si}_{14.47}\text{Mo}_{1.66}$	15.9	19.4	7624	0.16	2.6
$\text{Fe}_{3.84}\text{Co}_{67.05}\text{Ni}_{1.44}\text{B}_{11.51}\text{Si}_{14.47}\text{Mo}_{1.69}$	9.9	13.7	5087	0.28	2.5
$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	8.0	12.8	8967	0.23	2.8

Table 2. The long-wire composite with different wire diameter (D), wire period (b), and calculated plasma frequency (f_p).

Composite number	Wire composition	D, μM	b, mm	f_p , GHz
1	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	18.6	3	16.6
2	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	18.6	7	6.6
3	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	18.6	9	5.1
4	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	18.6	20	2.2
5	$\text{Fe}_{3.85}\text{Co}_{67.05}\text{Ni}_{1.44}\text{B}_{11.53}\text{Si}_{14.47}\text{Mo}_{1.66}$	15.9	7	6.6
6	$\text{Fe}_{3.85}\text{Co}_{67.05}\text{Ni}_{1.44}\text{B}_{11.53}\text{Si}_{14.47}\text{Mo}_{1.66}$	15.9	9	5
7	$\text{Fe}_{3.84}\text{Co}_{67.05}\text{Ni}_{1.44}\text{B}_{11.51}\text{Si}_{14.47}\text{Mo}_{1.69}$	9.9	9	4.9
8	$\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$	8.0	9	4.8

Magnetization and free space tests

The magnetic properties (magnetization, hysteresis loops and their parameters) of initial wire were determined by LakeShore VSM in the magnetic field up to 5 kOe at room temperature with the applied field parallel to the microwires axis.

The study of field tunable microwave response from wire-composites was carried out by free-space measurement techniques at frequency range 0.9-17 GHz in the presence of DC external magnetic field. An essentially uniform field up to 40 Oe in the area of $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$ was produced with a specially designed planar coil mounted on the planar composite sample. The coil is invisible for the irradiating wave when the current leads are perpendicular to the electrical field vector. The wires in composite are oriented along dc magnetic field. The detailed description of the free-space measurement was given in ref. [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first place, magnetic and structural properties of microwires were investigated. The diameter of the metal core (D) and overall microwires diameter (D_w) determined from SEM are shown in Table 1. Saturation magnetisation and coercive force were calculated from magnetisation hysteresis loop and also display in Table 1. The $\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ microwire shows a maximal value of magnetisation and anisotropy field.

Wire-based composite materials can be treated as continuous media at least in the irradiative near or far field region and can be then characterized by the effective

permittivity ϵ_{eff} . If the skin effect in wires is strong, ϵ_{eff} is determined by the wire geometry, lattice period, and the permittivity of the composite matrix [7]. In composite containing ferromagnetic wires exhibiting magnetic impedance (MI) effect at microwave frequency the effective permittivity depend on dc magnetic field [4]. In the case of long-wire composite the response of such array is similar to that of low-density plasma of very heavily charged particles, which is the consequence of confining the electrons within wires. As a result, for composites with continuous wires, the dispersion of the effective permittivity corresponds to that for diluted plasma [12]

$$\epsilon_{\text{eff}} = \epsilon - (\omega_p / \omega)^2, \quad (1)$$

with a characteristic plasma frequency:

$$\omega_p^2 = \frac{2\pi c^2}{b^2 \ln(b/a)}, \quad \omega_p = 2\pi f_p \quad (2)$$

where b is the spacing between the wires (cell parameters), a is the radius of metallic core of wire, c is velocity of light, ϵ is permittivity of matrix.

The study of tunable microwave response from wire-composites was conducted by modelling the effective permittivity and free-space measuring the transmission/reflection spectra. For the study of field tunable properties a dc external magnetic field applies to the composite by a planar coil. Fig. 1 demonstrates a microwave frequency dispersion of real and imaginary part of ϵ_{eff} with applied magnetic

Figure 1. Frequency plots of the real (solid) and imaginary (dash) part of effective permittivity of the composite containing $\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ continuous amorphous wires (sample #2) with the external field H_{ex} as a parameter.

field for the composite #2 (see Table 2). Both components are sensitive to external magnetic field in frequency range less 5 GHz. A drastic change of dispersion of permittivity is observed in field up to 2 Oe. The imaginary part opposite stronger changes in field above 2 Oe. The value of real part decrease and change sign at frequency below 2.5 GHz. However, using the parameters for this composite of $b = 7 \text{ mm}$ and $a = 9.3 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, the plasma frequency is 6.6 GHz. Below this frequency, the real part of the effective permittivity is negative with the absolute value strongly decreasing with increasing the field due to increase in the impedance of the wires. At frequency above the plasma frequency, the real part of ϵ_{eff} approaches to 1. Imaginary part of ϵ_{eff} vanishes with increasing frequency. So a field-tunable of both part of effective permittivity is observed at frequency range bellow plasma frequency. The plasma frequency values for other composite samples are listed in Table 2.

Since the effective permittivity parameter are calculating from S-parameter spectra, we can receive more information directly from dispersion of S-parameter. The 4 S-parameters (reflection S_{11} , S_{22} and transmission S_{12} , S_{21}) are measured during free space test. Fig. 2 shows frequency dependencies of reflection/transmission parameters S_{ij} of composite #2 at zero dc magnetic field. The investigated composites were characterized by the resonance type of the reflection spectra and effective permittivity with a strong dependence on the external field near a resonance plasma frequency. For composite sample #2 (see Table 2), S_{22} demonstrates a sharp peak at $f = 15.8 \text{ GHz}$.

Figure 2. Modulus of transmission (S_{12}) and reflection (S_{11} , S_{22}) spectra of the composite sample #2 containing $\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ ($D = 18.6$) continuous amorphous wires at $H_{\text{ex}} = 0 \text{ Oe}$.

Figure 3. Amplitude of transmission spectra S_{12} vs frequency for the composite sample #2 containing $\text{Fe}_4\text{Co}_{68.7}\text{Ni}_1\text{B}_{13}\text{Si}_{11}\text{Mo}_{2.3}$ ($D = 18.6$) continuous amorphous wires at different external dc fields.

There is a strong field dependence of transmission parameters at frequencies below and near the plasma frequency, due to the fact that associated resonances result in a different electromagnetic response with the effective permittivity of plasma type. The application of external field may decrease the transmission/reflection parameters due to the raise of absorption.

For a frequency near the plasma frequency of $f_p = 6.6$ GHz, the transmission parameter S_{12} decreases from -4.5 dB at $\text{Hex} = 0$ to -5.3 dB for $\text{Hex} = 5$ Oe (see Fig. 4). More strongly tunable effect of transmission parameter are found at $f = 4.3$ GHz which is below the plasma frequency. Thus reflection and transmission parameters of composite sample #3 demonstrate field-tunable properties at dc magnetic field up to 6 Oe. The strongest tunable effect of external field is observed for S_{22} parameter at frequency above the plasma frequency.

Fig. 4 displays S_{22} spectra under external dc magnetic field. At $f = 15.8$ GHz, S_{22} increases with external field (from -42 dB at $\text{Hex}=0$ to -32 dB at $\text{Hex} = 2$ Oe), as shown in the insertion to Fig. 3, and at field more than 2 Oe, S_{22} rapidly increases and reaches to -32 dB. The field dependence of S_{22} reaches saturation at field of about 5 Oe, which more or less correlate with anisotropy field of microwires.

Similar behaviour of S-parameters is observed for other composite samples. The maximum effect for reflection coefficient S_{11} and S_{22} was determined for composite

with wires spacing of 9 mm at frequency near 14 GHz. The resonance frequency of reflection parameters are observed at frequency above the plasma frequency calculated by using Equation (2).

Fig. 5 shows field dependencies of reflection parameter S_{22} of composite containing different wires with a same interwire space of 9 mm at the resonance frequency. The field dependencies of S_{22} are similar for different samples. Fig. 5a displays a slow rise of S_{22} from -45 dB at $H_{ex} = 0$ to -33 dB at a field $H_{ex} = 8$ Oe for composite sample #3. For comparison, in Fig. 5c, a slow change of S_{22} under magnetic field are shown, it increases from $S_{22} = -26$ dB ($H = 0$) to -21 dB ($H = 12$ Oe). The difference of these two composites can be attributed to the different diameter of wires. The diameter of wire used for composite #7 is about less than half of that used for composite #3, and the composition of wire are the same.

It has been established that planar composites are characterized by the resonance type of the reflection spectra. The resonance frequency depends on wire space and wire radius: the resonance frequency decreases with decreasing wire space and increases with increasing wire radius. Similar behaviour is demonstrated by plasma frequency (see eq. (2)). Thus, there exists a strong field dependence of transmission parameters S_{12} and S_{21} for frequencies below and near the plasma frequency and there is also strong field dependence of reflection parameters at frequency above the plasma frequency. Both effects can be of interest for sensing applications. With increasing frequency, there exists additional band showing the field effect, the origin of which is not clear.

Fig. 5b,d show the field dependencies of S_{22} for composite #6 and #7 with wire diameter 15.9 and 9.9 μm , respectively. In this composite, saturation occurs in field less than 4 Oe. The influence of field is less for composite with thinner wire. The distribution of saturation fields correlates with anisotropy field of microwire as summarized in Table 1.

Figure 4. (a) Modulus of reflection spectra S_{22} of the composite sample #2 at different external dc fields. The inset demonstrates S_{22} with H_{ex} as parameter: (1) -0 Oe; (2) -1 Oe; (3) -2 Oe; (4) -3 Oe; (5) -5 Oe.

(b) Field dependence of S_{22} of the composite sample #2 at frequency $f = 15.8$ GHz.

Figure 5. Field dependencies of reflection parameter S_{22} for different composite samples with wire spacing 9 mm, at the resonance frequencies.

CONCLUSION

In this work we have demonstrated field tunable planar composites containing long (50 cm) Co-based glass-coated microwires CoFeNiSiBMo by direct measurement and effective means of analysis. Transmission spectra of the wire, containing the media can be fairly narrow range of gap-related plasma frequency. A distinctive feature of this behavior is that changes in the structure of magnetic wires with weak magnetic field opens up bandwidth. The achieved tunability typically exceeds 10 dB for the external field of several Oe. Analysis of the spectra also changes depending on the magnetization in the wires.

It was found that there was a consistent correlation between magnetic properties of composite and geometry of the wire. It is concluded that this type of microwires is quite suitable for the manufacture of composite media sensing for local field detection. Thus, a systematic study of structural, mechanical, magnetic and microwave properties of Co-based magnetic microwires and composites containing these microwires were achieved. In the strong field dependence of reflection/transmission parameters and effective permittivity of composites containing long continuous wires indicate that these composites are very attractive candidate materials for a wide range of self-sensing applications. Certainly, further intensive research is needed to fully characterize the proposed microwave materials.

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